

Advances in large area robotically assisted OCT (LARA-OCT): Towards drive-by continuous motion imaging

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ABSTRACT

Optical coherence tomography is a powerful imaging technique to visualize and localize depth-dependent tissue structure to differentiate between healthy and pathological conditions. However, conventional OCT systems are only capable of detecting small areas. To overcome this limitation, we have developed a large area robotically assisted OCT (LARA-OCT) system for automatic acquisition of large OCT images. Using mosaic pattern acquisition and subsequent stitching, we previously demonstrated initial *in vivo* OCT skin images beyond 10 cm². To improve acquisition speed and reduce dead times, we here demonstrate and analyze LARA-OCT with a new drive-by continuous motion imaging protocol.

1. INTRODUCTION

Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) is a powerful imaging technique to visualize and localize depth-dependent tissue structures to differentiate between healthy skin and pathological conditions, such as inflammatory skin diseases [1]. Here, it is particularly valuable because, in contrast to skin biopsy, it is non-invasive and can provide instant diagnostic results. A major problem is that commercial, clinically approved OCT-systems are typically slow and not capable of scanning large areas at reasonable speed. Since skin lesions may extend over several square centimeters, imaging of larger skin lesions in their full extent would take several hours, leading to unacceptable discomfort of the patient. However, when imaging only a few representative regions of interest, potential inflammatory infiltrates remain undetected.

To overcome this limitation, we have developed a large area robotically assisted OCT (LARA-OCT) system. A collaborative robot system is combined with a home-built 3.3 MHz-OCT-system to allow automatic positioning of the OCT probe across the target. Robotically aligned OCT was already successfully demonstrated for retinal imaging by Draelos et al. [2]. They used a robot to position an ophthalmic OCT probe with the help of pupil and eye tracking cameras to compensate for subject motion and gaze while OCT scanning. Compared to ophthalmic imaging, our skin imaging application poses the challenge that large 3D datasets with file sizes beyond 1 TB and various shapes are to be acquired. In contrast to previous approaches for automatic large area scanning [3-5], we developed an intrinsic ODC-based, online probe-to-surface control for probe positioning and orientation while OCT imaging at real-time update rates. Using mosaic pattern acquisition and subsequent stitching, we previously demonstrated initial *in vivo* OCT skin images beyond 10 cm² (Figure 1).

However, as indicated by the green circles in the stitched OCT en face projection in Figure 1, basic 2D image stitching algorithms lead to stitching artifacts. Further, the total OCT acquisition speed is limited by the incremental acquisition process and related dead times. For less post-processing overhead due to stitching, reduced dead time and improved overall acquisition speed, continuous motion imaging is desirable. This “drive-by imaging” mode requires fast parallel processing, exact synchronization, and precise positioning of the OCT probe to ensure the acquisition of coherent large areas without motion artifacts. Thus, in this work we analyze the positioning precision and feasibility of LARA-OCT for continuous motion OCT imaging.

Figure 1 Stitched en face OCT intensity image of a human hand composed of 5×8 tiles. Green circles indicate stitching errors. The lower right insert visualizes a depth view at the indicated position (with 10x averaging of subsequent B-scans). Stitching was performed using Microsoft Image Composite Editor (Microsoft ICE V. 2.0.3.0, Microsoft Research, USA).

2. METHODS

The proposed LARA-OCT system consists of a home-built Fourier domain mode locked (FDML) laser-based 3.3 MHz-OCT-system [6], whose scan unit is mounted to the end effector of a 7-axis collaborative robot (Kuka-AG, LBR iiwa 14 R820, Germany). The scan unit, here sometimes also called OCT probe, includes a pair of galvanometer mirror scanners (dynAXIS 421, Scanlab GmbH, Germany) operated in a unidirectional scanning mode and simple scan lenses for telecentric scanning. The combined setup is visualized in Figure 2. All imaging experiments were conducted with 30 mW incident power on the sample and an OCT data acquisition rate of 4 GS/s with a sample depth of 12 bit (ATS9373, AlazarTech, Canada). The spectral bandwidth was set to 110 nm at a center wavelength of 1310 nm, resulting in an axial resolution of $8 \mu\text{m}$ in air.

For automatic alignment of the OCT probe towards the target, we developed a closed-loop probe-to-surface control algorithm. The software is based on LabVIEW (National Instruments, USA) and linked to the OCT imaging software via internal communication. It features three proportional feedback controllers (P-controllers) running in parallel with surface-height and -orientation as process variables. To detect the spatial surface position of the target, two OCT preview images are acquired crosswise in x - and y -directions and the surface is determined by edge detection (National Instruments, LabVIEW IMAQ Find Edge 2, USA). The center of gravity and orientation of the surface are determined by fitting lines into the detected edges and are sent to the P-controllers, where in response the pose of the robot is updated. This process currently runs at update rates of ~ 10 Hz and a measured accuracy of $\sim 15 \mu\text{m}$.

For standard MHz-OCT imaging procedures, typically a one-inch 50 mm spheric scan lens is used which leads to a lateral resolution of $22 \mu\text{m}$. Using this optical setup, we acquired initial continuous motion scans of an electronic breadboard, which is used as a target due to its regular pattern structure. Therefore, the slow y -galvanometer scanner is turned off while the OCT probe is constantly moved in positive y -direction within the world coordinate system by the robot arm. The cartesian robot velocity is set to 6 mm/s, while the fast x -galvanometer scanner is driven at 1.2 kHz to acquire 5 mm line scans. When starting the acquisition of a large OCT scan, the robot is triggered to constantly move for at least 20 s. In order to investigate the motion stability of the robot arm in more detail, we also performed drive-by imaging experiments using a LSM02 scan lens (LSM02, Thorlabs, USA), which facilitates $\sim 6.5 \mu\text{m}$ lateral resolution OCT imaging.

At the same scanning settings as described above, 1.5 mm line scans are acquired at continuous robot motion. A grid distortion target (R1L3S3P, Thorlabs, USA) is used as test sample and different acceleration and velocity settings are systematically investigated to analyze the performance of the proposed method.

Figure 2 Setup of the LARA-OCT system.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The continuous motion LARA-OCT imaging results are displayed in Figure 3. The OCT dataset of the breadboard consists of $1,024 \times 20,000 \times 1,200$ voxels, which corresponds to a file size of 48 GB. A field of view (FOV) of 100×5 mm was acquired within 16s, which is more than 10x faster than the overall acquisition speed of the same FOV in the mosaicking mode. As visible in the en face projection (Figure 3A), the acquisition trigger of the OCT system should be delayed to avoid data acquisition in the acceleration process of the robot arm, since more than half of the image is distorted due to non-constant robot motion. At constant speed, the image seems to be evenly sampled and only minor speed changes in y-direction or motion artifacts in orthogonal direction can be detected. The horizontal black line in the center features no obvious artifacts, indicating stability and no crosstalk in x-direction during orthogonal robot motion (Figure 3D). The surface irregularities visible in the B-scan representation of the dataset (Figure 3B and E) however indicate motion instabilities in z-direction during constant movements in y-direction. When analyzing the surface modulations more closely, height fluctuations of up to $100 \mu\text{m}$ were measured, which corresponds to the locked position values of the robot.

For detailed robot precision analysis, the drive-by mode was repeated with higher lateral resolution. Figure 3C exemplarily shows the OCT en face projection of a grid distortion target using a cartesian robot velocity of 90 mm/s. We chose this high speed, which is 40x faster than the scanning speed of the standard settings for the slow y-galvanometer scanner of the MHZ-OCT system, because we expect maximum possible robot instabilities at limit speed settings. As overlaid in the en face projection image (Figure 3C), a maximum deviation in x-direction (orthogonal to the robot motion) of $50 \mu\text{m}$ was determined. With respect to the typical lateral resolution of the MHZ-OCT system of $22 \mu\text{m}$ this crosstalk is negligible, especially when considering the drive-by mode for surgical navigation purposes. However, the evaluated stability tests show, that the temporary implementation of the LARA-OCT system and software is not applicable for high-resolution OCT imaging.

Figure 3 Continuous motion LARA-OCT images. A) OCT en face projection and B) B-scan of a breadboard with enlarged views at the indicated positions (D, E). C) OCT en face projection of a grid distortion target. In red the maximum deviation of the planned path is manually overlaid.

4. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In conclusion, LARA-OCT allows to acquire coherent, large areas using continuous robot motion. Compared to our previously demonstrated LARA-OCT images using mosaic pattern acquisition, we could improve the image acquisition speed by a factor of 10. Thus, it is a promising technique to screen or monitor large skin areas of patients with inflammatory skin disorders to possibly visualize subclinical skin alterations that would otherwise remain undetected. In order to use the system also for high-resolution OCT imaging with additional dynamic contrast, further investigations are needed to increase the motion precision of the robot or numerically correct for its' position error.

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